

CONSENT FORM FOR PROJECT PARTICIPANTS

Title of Project: Food Lives: Exploring household and neighbourhood food practices

Name of Researcher and School: Dr Katerina Psarikidou, SPRU, Dr Elaine Swan and Dr Jesse Hsu, School of Management

Please tick
 YES NO

- I consent to participate in the following activities with the researchers – tick as appropriate, choosing a maximum of 2:
 - Food maps YES NO
 - Interview YES NO
 - Participant pack YES NO

- I agree to allow the following to be audio-video recorded:
 - Food maps YES NO
 - Interview YES NO

- I have been briefed on the participant pack and understand that I must not take photographs of people without their consent. YES NO

- I consent to being informed about follow-up research activities and potential participation in future research. YES NO
- I have read the information sheet, had the opportunity to ask questions and I understand the principles, procedures and possible risks involved. YES NO

- I understand that personal data will be used for the purposes of this research study. I understand that such information will be treated strictly confidential and handled in accordance with [Data Protection legislation](#). YES NO

- I understand that any information given by me may be used in future reports, academic articles, publications or presentations by the researcher and the project team, but my personal information will not be included and I will not be identifiable. YES NO

- I understand that data will be kept according to the university guidelines for a minimum of 10 years after the end of the study. YES NO

- I understand that my participation is voluntary, that I can choose not to participate in part or all of the project, and that I can withdraw at any stage of the project without being penalised or disadvantaged in any way. YES NO
- I understand that I can no longer request withdrawal of my data from the project after 1st September 2022. YES NO

- I agree to take part in the above University of Sussex research project YES NO

Name:

Signature:

Date:

